

The Descriptive Study of Personality Santri Tahfidzul Qur'an 'Ainul Yaqin Campus Islamic Boarding School When Facing Polemics through the Deposit of Memorize Al-Qur'an

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ABSTRACT

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Based on observations made to Tahfidzul Qur'an students in the C class of the 'Ainul Yaqin Islamic boarding school, there is a unique phenomenon that formed by several aspects such as parenting, background, and education that can influence the regulation and self-control when facing a problem in daily life. The orientation in this research tries to reveal that students in dealing with daily problems are reflected when students experience problems with their memorization when depositing in front of the tahfidz teacher. The type of research used is qualitative which specifically in the process adopts a phenomenological approach. Data collection techniques and their instruments, researchers observe the subject directly and interview through the dissemination of questionnaires. While sequential data analysis techniques include, data collection, data condensation, data delivery, and conclusion making. The result obtained state that the diversity of the response of students who memorize the Al-Qur'an when facing obstacles with their memorization in front of the ability is a reflection of how students carry out self-control so that the tasks, trusts, and problems they encounter can be solved.

KEYWORDS:

Tahfidzul Quran Students Regulation and Self Control, Effect of Education on Quran Memorization, Ainul Yaqin Islamic Boarding School

1. INTRODUCTION

Human growth and development were originally formed from the environment in which it was located. The influence of the environment is very significant. It can be observed from the age of neonatal to be precise, namely, a newborn child and separated from his mother. At that age it can be known that the functioning of the ability of the mind and other sensory tools as a provision to receive, digest, and not be ready to synthesis knowledge except, hearing and vision that function. This is in line with the message contained in QS An-Nahl verse 78, that humans come to this world equipped with a set of gifts from him as a means of worship and carrying out learning activities (Ath-Thabari, 2007). The condition of a newborn human being still classified can only receive information that is provided by the environment for him passively. As time goes by following the growth and development of his age, human innate supplies such as other

five sense and reason will also function. According to Erickson (in Ahyani & Astuti, 2018) that, early age is a place where individuals start themselves to function as human by slowly values, norms, and whatever is around them will feel affected both from their nature, perspective on the surrounding environment, and physical behavior when experiencing problems or receiving certain stimuli. However, the mutual relationship between individuals and the environment becomes a problem even though every human being is a heterogeneous environment will certainly have implications for his behavior, attitude, and psychological condition (Putri, Putrawan, & Djamahar, 2022).

Furthermore, an individual towards adolescence to adulthood will continue to roll from one environment to another. After being in parenting, there will be an intervention in him from a new environment, for example, the world of education in which there is the influence of his peers so that it brings up other changes. There are three simple types of individuals during adolescence or puberty including, 1) experiencing development in their new environment with a pattern of progress that can be observed and in accordance with what their parents have instilled, 2) do not experience any changes and remain within the framework of the grower's

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norms of their parents, and 3) experiencing fluctuating changes both physically and psychologically that are difficult to read or look for an identity that he thinks is good, but contrary to what has been established by his parents. Every individual's development process certainly has risks that must be faced. As expressed by Sit (2012) & Resmalasari (2022) stated that changes in the form of obstacles or progress of goodness are caused and have an impact on their own environment. Thus, the responsibility of the people involved in the individual's life when there is an unwanted change or disturbance occurs, then teachers, parents, and other caregivers to immediately provide solutions in the form of stimuli according to their needs and capacities (Dianthiny & Rohman, 2021).

Various background of individual environmental conditions that are diverse to become a student. Then undergo education at an institution that according to his parents or personal self is good for him in the future. There is an interesting figure to be studied further and needs attention in the problem of managing his emotional intelligence, namely students. Specifically in this occasion are students memorizing Al-Qur'an. A student who establishes himself memorizing the Al-Qur'an needs a lot of preparation and readiness, indeed there are those who live like general students. As for memorizing the Al-Qur'an that needs to be prepared and readiness includes intellectual, physical, and emotional aspects. The integration of these three things as the basic capital to go to memorize the Al-Qur'an. This happens because memorizing the Al-Qur'an takes a long process and time so that patience, perseverance, habit, and order are the integrative applications of these three aspects (Noor & Pihasnawato, 2023). In addition to requiring the basis of readiness and preparation as before, according to Nuraeni, Sobari, & Supriatna (2023) stated that memorizing the Al-Qur'an also improves intellectual, physical, and emotional qualities. This condition can occur, because seeing the complex activities of memorizing the existing Al-Qur'an such as mandatory ziyadah, murojaah, and learning Islamic boarding school lessons or formal education affect the subject in such a way.

Regulation and self-control of Al-Qur'an memorization students are so varied in receiving stimuli for their daily activities. The response to the stimulus received affect the quality of memorization of Al-Qur'an memorization students. For students who can manage, program, and control themselves from various stimuli, activities that are so crowded are not an obstacle, but rather as an interesting challenge to be completed immediately in order to be able to carry out other activities as scheduled. However, such students are rarely found. The majority of students experience the opposite condition, besides there is an increase in the aspects that have been mentioned earlier in the density of activities making stimuli in a negative direction such as laziness, boredom, despair and so on (Noor &

Pihasnawato, 2023). If it has infected students, it will result in the quantity and quality of memorization. As for efforts to deal with existing problems so that they are not prolonged, this is where the role of the tahfidz supervisor positions himself as a mother figure. This is done in accordance with the theory that states that the mother figure is the most comfortable place to return for her children when facing problems, at that time there was an intervention to conduct counselling guidance (Annisa, 2023). The diversity of students of students with their background requires their teachers to be more or less required to understand the characteristics of each student. So that it makes it easier for teachers to guide students to memorize the Al-Qur'an after finding the patterns that are general.

Based on the result of observations with a long period of time carried out by researchers at Tahfidzul Qur'an students in class C Islamic boarding school 'Ainul Yaqin Campus from 2015 to 2024. Researchers found a unique pattern formed from the accumulation of stimuli in several aspects such as parenting, background, and education affecting regulation and self-control of students in overcoming their daily problems, researchers found that they spontaneously appeared when depositing memorization. This is also observed when several students who are subjects are given more responsibilities outside of existing obligations where each individual gives various responses. The response is the same as when students depositing memorization have problems such as being wrong or forgetting at the beginning, in the middle, or even when facing there is a blank in their memory, so they need the guidance of the memorizing to memorize them. Regarding the response of existing students, when welcoming the reading talqin from the person, it is detected that the response as a form of regulation and self-control of the students has the same pattern, namely when the person concerned responds to problems in daily life and when welcoming the reading talqin from the guardian.

As for the obstacles experienced by students who memorize the Al-Qur'an related to their memorization, namely that there is a problem as in the previous paragraph in Freud's eyes, known as psychopathology. Psychopathology is a scientific discourse that studies the symptoms of abnormalities and abnormalities related to behavioral conditions, cognitive intelligence, and inner conditions (Maslahat, 2019).

The temporary strong guess obtained by the researcher is that this variety of compound responses is a picture of the student's personality in facing problems in their daily life outside of memorizing their memorization activities. Thus, based on the presentation and analysis result of this research researcher, it is necessary and interesting to carry out further deepening in the hope that the result of this scientific work will contribute in the form of scientific treasures to the world of education, Islamic boarding school, and Islam.

II. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

From the research carried out, the researcher obtained several data, namely the results of observations and questionnaire responses from students who described the personality of tahfidzul qur'an students when they encountered problems both outside and when they were in memorization class. During the period since, the first time he became a student of tahfidzul Qur'an until this year, approximately eight years. Researchers in the past year have found a unique phenomenon that needs to be studied deeply. The phenomenon is about the personality pattern of students when depositing their memorization and behavior outside the classroom when they get trust, responsibilities, or problems that are suddenly given to them.

The first description discussed the results of the observation of tahfidzul qur'an students in class when depositing memorization. Researchers understand that every student who memorizes the Al-Qur'an in general or partially, especially the students of the TQ C 'Ainul Yaqin Campus Islamic Boarding School UNISMA started from individuals with heterogeneous backgrounds. This plurality affects the quality of memorization of students who require double focus, namely cognitive and mental aspects. This compound condition also requires researchers to be able to understand, study, guide, and position themselves according to the conditions and obstacles experienced by students. Specifically, the role of the researcher takes time for students to experience obstacles when memorizing deposits are listened to directly. This guidance process is observed periodically, so that it finds patterns from the personality of the students concerned when facing problems.

Every student who memorizes has problems when researchers do guidance or remind inappropriate parts and even there is a verse reading error, they give a response. The response by the researcher is classified into several categories. As for the classification category of student responses, including 1) the gestures remain calm, can still continue their memorization after experiencing obstacles and the researcher is reprimanded, 2) the gestures are still calm but, when they experience problem in their memorization and are then reprimanded by researchers, they need time to think. Then reordering memories and collecting self-preparedness then he will be able to continue his memorization, 3) his gestures begin to fluctuate along with the quality of memorization he has. Mostly in third case, if the student cannot exercise self-control, then the memorization will be difficult to determine as it was good as before.

Then the reason why each student experiences obstacles will be explained by the researcher in the following questionnaires results section.

There are two types of questions in the questionnaire, of which there are four in total, consisting of one multiple choice and other three essay questions where each student is given space to provide a variety of answers. Based on the first

question from the questionnaire about how students respond to real-life problems that arise suddenly, the following data is obtained. Of the 16 respondents, there are 10 students who are classified in the category of needing time to think in solving problems, 10 confident students to solve problems, 1 student experiencing disorders in the form of panic and fear, and 1 student who does not care about the problems they are facing. Based on the first question, the majority of students need time to think when they encounter problems. As for the data in summary, if it is stated in the form of a table as follows.

Table 1. Classification of Student Responses Related to Real Life Problems that Appear Suddenly

Category	Percentage of Santri
Be confident	25%
It takes time to think	62.5%
Panic and fear	6.3%
Can't think	0%
Don't care	6.3%

The second question is a follow-up form of the first question on the form of multiple choice. The purpose of this second question is an effort by researchers to get honest and more in-depth information from the subject of the interview concerned. Then the researcher obtained the research results data around why students respond to problems in life that arise spontaneously as selected in the previous number. In this case, the researcher wants to present a sample of student description responses based on the classification of answer categories contained in table 1 as follows.

A. Confident santri.

“Confidence, because if we are not confident, it will not even run smoothly, for example when the deposit condition is not confident that we must be smooth, it will have an impact on the future when it is advanced in front of the ustadz/ustadzah, the one who will be deposited must be chaotic whether it is lost, forgotten etc.”

B. Santri who needs time to think.

The first student's response.

“I need time to think about solving it because I am afraid to take the action that can make the problem I am facing fatal, for that I need time to take the next step and estimate the impact of the steps I take”.

The second student's response.

“When depositing and being reprimanded, I need time to think first, then try to repeat while remembering” to justify the mistake earlier, it applies when I am very ready for the deposit”

C. Panicked and scared students.

“Panic, because I'm afraid if I make the wrong decision”.

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D. Santri who doesn't care.

"It just happened. Usually if there is a problem it is only thought about temporarily, if it has been overturned (for example crying or watching Netflix) it will gradually forget".

Based on the exposure to the student response that has been classified, an information about individual students can be found in responding to a problem with different orientations and solutions. For students who have a strong sense of self-confidence, their ability to control their thoughts, minds, and gestures has given enough to encourage themselves to complete their responsibilities or problems they are facing. In fact, the opposite will be applied if students who have this sense of self-confident are disturbed or experience refraction, it will be difficult to find a solution in the future.

Santri who need time to think in his efforts to solve problems. This is related to his perspective on a problem paying attention to some of the possibilities that will occur and wanting to take the best steps. The time interval between students and their actions in dealing with the responsibilities, problems, and trusts carried out, is used to prepare themselves carefully. The maturity of preparation that can measure his personal self. If other people try to intervene forcing unmaturing preparations, they will get a less than optimal and even fatal impact.

Santri in the category experience panic when they find a new problem caused because there is no picture., preparation, or can be congenital from an early age. A person who experiences panic at least needs time to restore focus which will later have implications for his ability to deal with a problem.

The last category is a santri who doesn't care about the problems they face. In fact, it doesn't matter, but in his mind all the problems that exist are to be faced and then will definitely find a solution in the middle of the road.

Based on student's exposure based on the category, of course, it can be said that the responses that have been expressed do not simply appear spontaneously. Of course, there are those who background or shape it, so that it can give birth to the response to the stimulation that exists in a problem. Then problems, responsibilities, trusts, duties and so on for students become stimuli that must be resolved. In solving it, it is not only that those who are included in the category of confidence can complete everything individually, especially regarding the memorization of the Al-Qur'an, which is actually a scared matter, so it needs the presence of a support system that is used as a mother figure in guiding her to memorize the Al-Qur'an to the end. The role is held by the tahfidzul qur'an class or the researcher himself.

Regarding a person who is considered to have a maternal nature in accepting shortcomings, a place to complain, the figure who heard his advice is the tahfidz teacher or the researcher himself. Continuing from the previous question, the figure of the support system is very necessary to escort students to fulfil their obligations, for

tahfidz teachers it is also necessary to pay attention, because each student has its own limits during the coaching process. Thus, it is necessary to make an explicit statement about the perspective of the tahfidzul qur'an santri to view the memorization teacher as follows.

"He is a teacher who is diligent with students. Even though I wasn't smooth, he led my reading until I finished it. He also often motivates us so that we are passionate about memorizing and continuing to improve our memorization. For me, there is no fault in him being our teacher".

"When listening to memorization, the ustadz listens well, even though sometimes I forget the continuation of the verse or forget in the middle of the verse, the ustadz fixes it slowly".

"I apologize in advance if I personally when listening to memorization sometimes there is a fear of being wrong because ustadz Yunus himself listens to 2 people in 1 sitting so I am afraid if I forget to deposit memorization and it will actually trouble the ustadz".

It can be observed from the exposure of students who are used as research subjects who put forward the figure of a tahfidz teaching teacher according to the experience and background of students so far. There are three interesting points of view in looking at the figure of a tahfidz teacher who can be classified into, namely, 1) the first response, students whose memorization is good and rarely have problems, so that what is given or needed is motivation, 2) the second response, students whose memorization rarely encounter obstacles, but when obstacles occur they quickly make improvements. Therefore, as a level of warning with gentleness, and 3) the third response, students who often experience problems in their memorization such as split focus when the atmosphere is not conducive, sick, lack of preparation, so that when things interfere with their concentration which result in memorization, their heart condition experiences anxiety which expressed in fear of wrong worry.

After reviewing the confessions of several subjects and analyzing them about the assessment of the tahfidz teacher, the researcher asked more in-depth questions regarding how the student's condition was honest when they going, sedan, and finished memorizing them. This is needed for researchers because the recognition of previous questions needs to be re-deepened. It is not enough just a teacher figure in general, but it needs to be reviewed in more depth regarding contextual experiences in the field when going, being, and after depositing memorization. The statement of students is shown by the researcher as follows.

A. Confident santri

"When I will move forward if it is really sure I am ready, god willing, I will be confident when I am ready, I can be easier to focus and can increase my confidence, when I finish the deposit, I will be relieved".

B. Students who need time to think

“When going forward, you must have prepared the memorization carefully because it must be what you want is smooth, when it is in front of the ustadz I try to focus even though sometimes the focus is still broken because of “confused and fighting with a loud voice” whether muroja’ah or the deposit, after completing the deposit, thank God, it’s a relief, especially if it goes smoothly from the beginning, the end is very happy, masyaallah”.

C. Santri who is afraid and panic

“When going forward, I sometimes feel heavy afraid of not going smoothly when depositing. Sometimes this happens when I don’t have memorization and I’m not fluent in memorization. However, when I want to move forward, I usually encourage myself with ‘bismillah can do it, if it’s not smooth, it’s okay for us to launch it tomorrow, bismillahirrahmanirrahim’. Then when I’m depositing memorization, I memorize well, usually in the middle or at the end of the verse, there must be an error, and when the error is corrected by the ustadz, I will suddenly be blank and focused about what the next verse is. But at that time, I tried to focus, calm down so that I could imagine the sequent verse. And when I finished the deposit, I felt relieved, there was no more burden, and continued to prepare memorization for tomorrow”.

D. Santri who doesn’t care

“When I’m going forward, my heart feels normal, but when I’m in front of ustadz Yunus sometimes my memorization is blank, because of the lack of memorization preparation but, when it’s steady with memorization I try to focus on launching deposits, after completion I’m relieved when it’s smooth and sometimes I’m also sad/ashamed when my memorization is not smooth”.

Based on the description of the result of interviews and observations, researchers found a special pattern of the uniformity of the response of the tahfidzul qur’an students. Several students who are respondents are infected with psychopathology with the aim of defending themselves so that they can continue their memorization in front of their students. The reason researchers concluded that students of tahfidzul qur’an experienced psychopathology because of obstacles that are often experienced by students who memorize the Al-Qur’an are associated with reason and memory such as sudden forgetting, easy to forget, not focused, and lack of concentration (Wahidah, 2016). The classification of psychopathology experienced by students memorizing the Al-Qur’an is 1) errors in remembering foreign words and 2) errors in remembering names and word orders (Freud, 2015). Both of these things are described contextually through individual memories that tend to fade easily in new vocabulary in foreign languages and forget

about the sequences, especially when getting into trouble. In line with the theory put forward by Prasetya & Hidayah (2023) which suggests that psychopathology is a representation of a disturbed psychological condition, so that it has an impact on the inner state, mind, and self-control in dealing with emotions begins to decline.

Then the mental fluctuations of students get stronger if their health condition, emotional mood, unstable mind, and experience other disorders. The conditions that affect the quality of memorization appear when students lack self-control, because of many responsibilities that must be completed simultaneously, lack of self-confidence, and an anxious perspective on them when facing for memorization deposits. The decrease in self-control on self-emotions causes a tendency to behave negatively, so there are several things that are also affected such as interactions between individuals, cognitive functions, and productivity (Rahayu & Irsyadiyah, 2022). Thus, researchers get conclusion taken from the memorization of the Al-Qur’an students in front of their guardians, because memorization is classified as a wrong problem that must be accounted for every day, so that when students get reciprocity from memorization that is completed, it reflects how the students face problems in their daily life. As for the detailed conclusion as follows 1) students with good self-control have a high sense of self-confidence that they can account for their memorization in front of the memorization and want to accept advice from their teachers as a form of counseling guidance for self-improvement, 2) students who have self-control are classified as need enough time and preparation to establish themselves in order to minimize fatal errors, 3) students who lack self-control begin in themselves to respond with panic or anxiety, then the presence of memorization builds strengthening self-control.

III. CONCLUSION

The personality of the students who memorize the Al-Qur’an when facing the polemic of contextual problems studied through a series of research procedures that have been determined to get a result that the plurality of responses of students who memorize the Al-Qur’an when facing obstacles in their memorization in front of the memorization is a reflection of how the students respond, face, complete, and are responsible for the tasks, trusts, and problems they encounter because the deposit of memorization of the Al-Qur’an is a concrete form of responsibility that must be completed as soon as possible in front of the memorization forgiving to complete the next memorization.

As for the next results found by the researcher that from sixteen respondents in this case, only 25% have good self-control with indications of readiness and confidence when solving problems that arise suddenly. Based on the description of the interview and observations, it appears when the student experiences obstacles or forgetfulness and the memorization gives the wrong cues, so in the cognitive and

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mental aspects he has found the correct reading with confidence. There are 62, 5% of students who need time to indicate that self-control is at a sufficient level. Referring to the description of interviews and observations, students who belong to that type when they experience obstacles or forgetfulness and memorization give wrong cues, then students respond silently for a moment to organize themselves by reading slowly the previous verse until they are cognitive and they are mentally sure to find the right reading with confidence. And 6,3% of students experience panic and fear which indicates that their self-control is not good. Students who are included in the category of experiencing panic and fear when experiencing problems or forgetfulness and memorization give wrong cues, then students respond nervously, memorization is not organized, cannot continue memorization because they forget, which condition cannot be forced. The only way is to need the presence of a supervisor who can guide until it is really complete with the consequences of the student's dependence or provide an opportunity to prepare themselves carefully but still in the supervision of the supervisor.

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